

ISic1433

I.Sicily inscription 1433

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Megara Hyblaea

Place of origin (modern)

Megara Iblea

Provenance

in situ, in the hellenistic walls

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Megara Hyblaea, in situ

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI330077

1. Ἀριστίο^ονο [ς]

2. Νίσιος.

3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644976

EDCS 64800227

PHI 330077

Bibliography

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